

OPISI-DE: German Translation and Cultural Adaptation of the Occupational Performance Inventory of Sexuality and Intimacy

Authors

Markus Kraxner, MSc | Professor, Occupational Therapy faculty, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences (CUAS) | Carinthia, Austria | m.kraxner@fh-kaernten.at

Katja Stolte, BSc | Occupational Therapist, Sex Educator, coitoergosum | Berlin, Germany

Sabine Walgram, BSc | Senior Lecturer, Occupational Therapy faculty, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences (CUAS) | Carinthia, Austria

Beth Ann Walker, PhD, MS, OTR, FAOTA | Professor, School of Occupational Therapy, University of Indianapolis | Indianapolis, Indiana, USA

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Abstract

Importance: Sexuality and intimacy are integral to human occupation, yet there is a scarcity of resources in German that address these aspects in occupational therapy.

Objective: To adapt and translate the Occupational Performance Inventory of Sexuality and Intimacy (OPISI) into German, ensuring cultural relevance and comprehension for practice in German-speaking regions.

Design: A methodical multistep translation and adaptation process was employed, including initial translation, feedback from occupational therapy experts and potential end-users, review and synthesis, back-translation, layout, and free-access-publication.

Setting & Participants: The translation and adaptation process involved both online and in-person collaborative sessions. Structured feedback on the current state of the translation was collected from two distinct groups (12 occupational therapy experts and 10 potential end-users) from Germany, Switzerland, and Austria utilizing the digital platform LimeSurvey.

Results: A total of 1,377 changes were made to the original OPISI documents, encompassing linguistic, cultural, and content-related modifications. These were thoroughly examined and incorporated into the final German version, the OPISI~DE.

Conclusions and Relevance: The culturally adapted OPISI~DE provides German-speaking occupational therapists with a robust tool for assessing and addressing sexuality and intimacy in clinical practice, thus filling a significant gap in the field. This contributes to the enrichment of occupational therapy practice and client care within German cultural contexts. Free open-access to the OPISI~DE is available with registration at <https://uindy.edu/health-sciences/ot/opisi-de>.

What This Article Adds

This brief report describes the process of the translation and cultural adaptation of the Occupational Performance Inventory of Sexuality and Intimacy (OPISI) into German, named OPISI~DE. The easy availability of the OPISI~DE will contribute to addressing sexuality and intimacy with clients within the OT process in German-speaking countries.

Introduction/Background

Human existence encompasses various fundamental elements, which persist throughout life, including sex, gender identities and roles, sexual orientation, eroticism, pleasure, intimacy, and reproduction (WHO, 2006). Sexuality and intimacy are recognized as integral components of a person's occupational identity, irrespective of the presence of illness, injury, disability, or consequence of aging. Occupational therapy practitioners possess unparalleled expertise in comprehending and lessening the influence of client factors, performance skills and patterns, and contextual demands to enhance optimal engagement and performance in valued occupations pertaining to sexuality and intimacy (Walker, 2020). Despite the acknowledgment that sexual concerns can greatly hinder clients' occupational performance (Rose & Hughes, 2018; Sakellariou & Sawada, 2006), there is a widespread deficiency in guidelines and resources available to help practitioners effectively address these concerns. As a result, discussions regarding sexuality in clinical practice tend to be brief or, in some instances, completely disregarded (Areskoug-Josefsson et al., 2016). This is especially true in German-speaking countries – though various authors have addressed this issue and tried to move the profession forward in this regard (Raß, 2020; Schneider & le Granse, 2018; Stolte, 2022a), and concepts for teaching regarding sexuality and intimacy exist (Stolte, 2022b).

In 2020, Walker developed the Occupational Therapy Sexual Assessment Framework (OTSFAF) to serve as the theoretical foundation for the scope of practice for occupational therapy. The OTSAF depicts a pathway from intrinsic to extrinsic. In sum, a person's client factors (sexual knowledge, sexual self-view), body structures, and body functions (sexual interest, sexual response) influence the performance of relevant occupations (sexual activity, intimacy, sexual expression, sexual health, and family planning) that occur within an individual's context. Walker then used the OTSAF to develop the Occupational Performance Inventory of Sexuality and Intimacy (OPISI), which is an occupation-focused screen, assessment, and performance measure. Since its release in English in an online open-access format in 2020, the OPISI has been accessed by thousands of occupational therapists worldwide. Translation and cultural adaptation of these tools in non-English languages are needed. The first and the second authors pursued the translation and cultural adaptation of the OPISI to German, after the instrument was introduced in the podcast "OT After Dark" (2021) to empower German-speaking occupational therapists to address these topics better – hopefully true to the call to action from Auger et al. (2022) to improve and inform practice, teaching and research in Germany, Austria, German-speaking parts of Switzerland, and beyond to facilitate a more holistic treatment of clients in diverse settings.

Method

Research Design and Study Protocol

After initial contact with the original author, permission to use, translate, and adapt the OPISI was obtained from the original author and the University of Indianapolis in Indiana. After a screening of best practices regarding translation and cultural adaptation (Beaton et al., 2000; Costa, 2014; Uhrmann et al., 2019), a modified 12-step process from permission to publication was defined and implemented by the researchers, depicted in a summarized form in Figure 1. The research process in which participants' feedback was collected was conducted online using LimeSurvey.

Figure 1: Process-steps for the translation and cultural adaptation of the OPISI into German.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

This study was reviewed by the University of Indianapolis Human Research Protection Program. Given the purpose of the study to translate the OPISI and collected data by participants related to readability and clarity of translated items, it was determined the study did not meet the criteria for human subjects research. Extensive data protection measures for participants in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union (EU) were implemented during the whole process. This included, e.g., informed consent, the use of a survey platform self-hosted on servers physically owned and maintained by the Carinthia University of Applied Sciences (CUAS), and the survey design itself.

Participants

Participants consisted of two cohorts, Group A (OT-experts) and Group B (potential end-users of the OPISI-DE), and were recruited online, using purposeful, snowball, and convenience sampling (Denscombe, 2010, p. 34-38). Existing networks (e.g., professional associations, self-help groups, umbrella organizations for specific diseases), social media, and newsletters were utilized in the recruiting process. Interested persons from both groups pre-registered online for participation. Final participation in Group A was dependent on the fulfillment of specific requirements (years of experience as an occupational therapist, experience in the topics of sexuality and intimacy, and country of residence). No restrictions were applied for participants in Group B. In Group A, 61 persons were pre-registered. After pre-registration, participants were matched for country of residence and experience; 12 persons were enrolled (six each from Austria and Germany). In Group B, ten persons pre-registered, and all were enrolled.

Survey-content, -design and translation/adaptation procedure

Both surveys were conducted consecutively, specifically Group B's survey commenced only after results from Group A's survey on the content of the OPISI had been reviewed and implemented. Group A was presented on an item-per-item-base with the full content of the OPISI, excluding the manual, Group B was presented in the same manner with the contents of the initial screen and the in-depth-inventory of the OPISI, since these are the forms end-users are filling out on their own when the OPISI is applied. All participants were asked if the German wording of the items was clearly understandable to them. If not, participants were asked to provide suggestions for adapting/re-wording the item. Since both surveys were extensive in scope and the amount of time necessary to complete them, design principles to reduce survey fatigue (de Koning et al., 2021), such as using simple language, completion reminders, the possibility of saving and continuing the survey and the option to be thanked in the OPISI-DE-manual as an incentive were implemented iteratively.

Group A's survey consisted of the item content after the initial translation, which was reviewed, modified, and culturally adapted by the first, second, and last author before implementation therein. Group B's survey likewise consisted of the discussed and implemented consensus feedback from Group A's survey, which was reviewed, modified, and adapted in the same fashion. The feedback of Group B's survey was implemented likewise. This consolidated German version was translated back to English through a different translation bureau than the initial translation and reviewed, discussed, and finalized by the first, second, and last authors. The OPISI-DE manual

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was not reviewed by participant groups but was modified, culturally adapted, expanded, and updated by the first and second authors. All changes therein were made in coordination with the original author.

Data Analysis

Data entered in the surveys through participants was not analyzed statistically beyond descriptive aspects for reasons we discuss later. A content-analysis framework was developed to categorize the nature of changes made to the contents of the documents, consisting of three categories (content, cultural, and formal changes), which are used in the following section.

Results

Participants

Out of the selected twelve participants in Group A, three from Germany and four from Austria completed the expert survey entirely. On average, the experts were 42 years old, had 19 years of experience as occupational therapists, and 12 years specifically in the field of sexuality and intimacy. Gender-wise, six of the seven participants identified as female and one as male. Seven completed surveys have been gathered from end-users in Group B. Participants had a mean age of 47 years and an average of 17 years of experience with limitations or challenges related to sexuality and intimacy. Four participants in this group identified as female and three as male.

Change and adaptation process

From the initial translation by a translation agency to the final version of each document, a total of 1,377 changes were made. In this process, experts were consulted, end-users were involved, the German version was translated back to English to be discussed with the original author, sent to a proofreading agency for a final check regarding spelling and grammar, and, as a last step, the layout of the OPISI~DE was finalized by CUAS' marketing department.

The OPISI consists of individual documents, which are the Manual, Initial Screening, In-Depth Inventory, Performance Measure, Goal Page, and the Referral Form. The translation process from OPISI to OPISI~DE resulted in numerous changes in the individual documents.

As shown in Figure 2, the number of changes were 681 for the Manual, 83 for the Initial Screening, 466 for the In-Depth Inventory, 128 for the Performance Measure, 6 for the Goal Page, and 13 for the Referral Form.

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Figure 2: Number of changes during translation and adaptation per document.

Categories

All changes that were made were assigned to the following categories: content, cultural, and formal changes. The category of content changes consists of changes for improved or simplified comprehensibility, content-related errors, newly written paragraphs, etc. The category of cultural adaptations consists of changes in the use of gender-sensitive language and cultural adaptation to the German-speaking regions where OPISI~DE will be used. The category of formal changes includes all adaptations regarding punctuation, adjustment of bullet points, paragraphs, etc. As shown in Figure 3, this resulted in a total of 989 content changes, 55 cultural changes, and 333 formal changes.

Figure 3: Number of changes during translation and adaptation per category.

Publication and accessibility

One overarching goal of this work has been free and easy accessibility to the OPISI-DE and usability for occupational therapists and their clients, as well as wide dissemination of the instrument, to increase awareness of the importance of the topic of sexuality and intimacy in occupational therapy in German-speaking areas. For this purpose, a dedicated page has been set up on the University of Indianapolis website in German through which one can access the OPISI-DE through a short and simple registration.

To ensure wide dissemination of OPISI-DE among occupational therapists, we used various channels such as oral presentations (Kraxner, M., Stolte, K., Walgram, S., & Walker, B. A. 2023), articles (Kraxner & Stolte, 2023), and podcasts (Heizmann & Striesow, 2023) in which the project as well as the completed OPISI-DE were introduced and elaborated on.

Discussion

The purpose of this work was to engage in a global collaboration to translate and culturally adapt the OPISI for use in German-speaking countries and to make it available to occupational therapists in an easy and convenient way. We included perspectives and viewpoints of occupational therapists and potential end-users in the adaptation process on the content and items of the OPISI. The thoroughness of the process did impact the original version; for example, one item of the performance measure regarding sexual self-view was not in alignment with the scoring instructions used, and this item was rephrased in both the English and German versions. Though our work has some methodical limitations that are discussed below, we are convinced that the availability of the OPISI-DE solidifies the scope of OT in addressing sexuality and intimacy, advances global practice, and benefits German-speaking clients around the world. Sexuality and intimacy are essential factors of the human experience regardless of geographic location. These topics are important, not only on an individual level but also within a broader perspective: the WHO's Package of Interventions for Rehabilitation (2023) explicitly designates "sexual functions and intimate relationships" as one of the functioning domains of rehabilitation (p. 7) and occupational therapists as "rehabilitation specialists" (p. 8). Consequently, addressing these topics by our profession is essential, and the OPISI-DE provides a structured way of achieving this in diverse settings, thus contributing to better overall service quality and to the well-being of clients.

Limitations

Some limitations should be considered regarding the methodical approach: the final sample size of both survey groups was small despite extensive recruiting measures in Germany and Austria. In the occupational therapy expert group, we prioritized an equal number of participants from each country, which led to a smaller sample size. The required expertise regarding sexuality and intimacy in both groups was self-reported and taken at face value, and no formal validation (e.g., through advanced training certificates, or diagnoses) was performed. Due to the limited scope of the study, no statistical analyses regarding agreement levels between the two groups were performed, though this opens avenues of research regarding validity- and reliability aspects in German-speaking countries.

Conclusions

Through an effective global collaboration, the German version of the OPISI, the “Handlungsperformanz-Inventar für Sexualität und Intimität (OPISI~DE)“ has been culturally adapted and made available online to occupational therapy practitioners in German-speaking countries through a free and open-access download via <https://uindy.edu/health-sciences/ot/opisi-de>. A diverse dissemination strategy (congress presentations, articles, podcasts, social media) was pursued to inform as many colleagues as possible of the availability – the OPISI~DE has been downloaded more than 392 times since publication. The availability of the OPISI~DE to educators, practitioners, and researchers provides further possibilities for integrating the topics of sexuality and intimacy in these areas.

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